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NEW NEOLOGISMS IN SOCIAL NETWORKING

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ABSTRACT

Today's Era is known as digital age and the reason for that is social media. With advancement of technology and social networking, the words we speak are also changing. The origin and spread of neologisms are in many ways related to the development of social networking. Nowadays we encounter a number of neologisms not only in science and technology, but also in all areas of science, official, conversational, social media as well. This article provides information on using of neologisms in internet-based communication, for which purpose the examples from the most popular social networks have been extracted.

Since the internet has been emerged and people began using it for fast chatting, emailing, commenting and communicating. Therefore, notable amount of freshly created expressions have come into everyday usage.

Some have been derived from new technology, equipment, programme or even an online game. People cannot imagine their lives without their mobiles, computers, tablets which are mostly useless without the internet connection. This technology revolution has affected our private lives, working conditions, socializing in everyday life. No wonder brand new expressions have been developed over the last twenty or more years. In the first place, social networking is the area that, makes remarkable contribution to new lexical elements.

There will be investigated ten examples in respect of their meaning as explained on <https://www.vappingo.com/word-blog/great-examples-of-neologisms/> and the particular way the new word was created. It should also be highly interesting to search its origins and roots in history.

Tweet cred

According to *The Urban Dictionary* online *tweed cred* is like a street cred and means a social standing or a kind of respect you gain from your humorous, cool and intelligent tweets. Therefore "tweet" is the status or any contribution put on twitter and the word "cred" is the abbreviation of "credit". It can be assumed this to classify as a compound "Tweet cred" together with clipping of "credit" to form the second part "cred".

404

404 is someone who is clueless. From the World Wide Web error message 404 Not Found, meaning that the requested document could not be located. Undoubtedly, this is a remarkably new “word” because it actually is not a word but a number. However, it is really arguable as for identifying the word formation process. It could be assumed 404 is a coinage

Crowdsourcing

Crowdsourcing is the activity of getting a large group of people to contribute to a project or task, especially by using a website where people can make contributions; for example, online proofreading services. Apparently, this is a compound of crowd and sourcing, thus joining these two words together to form a name for modern activity.

Geobragging

Repeated status updates noting your location in an attempt to get attention or make other people jealous. Geo is surely blended from geography and bragging which means busting has been joined to form a new coinage “geobragging”. Thus this is a compound formed from one clipped word and another full word.

Unfriend

As the opposite of friend but in connection with any social network where people have lists of contacts – friends who they have added gradually. EOLD briefly defines *unfriend* as a verb “to remove (someone) from a list of friends or contacts in a social networking site”.

When examining the way of formation *unfriend* is a derivation from noun to verb affixed with the negative prefix *un-*.

Selfie

Defined in the EOLD *selfie* is an informal term, noun referring to “a photograph that one has taken of oneself, typically one

taken with a smartphone or webcam and shared via social media.” To explain the way it was formed the noun *self* has taken a suffix – ie. Therefore, it can be labelled as derivation.

Wall

Apart from its original meaning that comes from the Latin “*vallum*” in the internet world this word started to be used as something completely different. *Wall* is the virtual space on your social networking profile where you can display and share photos, feelings, videos, etc. and other members can see it. This is a metaphor denoting new meaning.

Like

It is not a secret that like can stand for a noun as well as for a verb while its meaning is to have a positive attitude, sympathy to something. Nevertheless, in social networking world this is a button for giving somebody a “*thumbs up*” as to react to somebody’s contribution.

Troll

From the Old Norse *troll* is an ugly creature usually a giant or a dwarf from Swedish folklore. People started using this term in connection with someone who keeps bothering others by posting rude comments on Facebook or other social networks.

Tweet

From this onomatopoeic expression that originally refers to the sound made by birds developed into the name of a post on the social media application Twitter. According to the EOLD *tweet* can also be used as a verb in the same sense.

It is obvious that *wall*, *like*, *troll* and *tweet* are all social networking metaphors.

To sum up, neologisms stand for innovation in every language and as they are created every day. As it will be seen in

the paper, metaphor has enriched the world of social networking sites with the most new words. Neologisms such as, wall, like, troll and tweet all have gained new meanings together with the development of the virtual communication. Therefore, these words have started to be used in completely different connotations than originally. While the internet has been

launched the new things, new meanings came to the language. Using metaphor might be evaluated as the easiest way of inventing new terms. Social networking sites try hard to be accessible to anyone from young age to the elderly. That is the reason why their language needs to be as simple as possible.

References:

1. Arnold I.V. The English Word. M. 1973
2. Crystal, D. (2001). Language and Internet. Cambridge, UK: Cambridge University Press
3. "54 Great Examples Of Modern Day Neologism," <https://www.vappingo.com/word-blog/great-examples-of-neologisms/>
4. <http://www.urbandictionary.com/>
5. <http://rdues.bcu.ac.uk/neologisms.shtml>
6. <https://www.theguardian.com/books/2013/apr/17/tom-chatfield-top-10-internet-neologisms>
7. Azimjon Latifjon oqli Melikuziev. (2022). HISTORICAL AND MODERN CLASSIFICATION OF PARALINGUISTICS. *Academia Globe: Inderscience Research*, 3(10), 126–128. <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/UAH57>
8. Khakimov, M. K., & Ugli Melikuziev, A. L. (2022). The History of Paralinguistic Researches. *International Journal of Culture and Modernity*, 13, 90-95.
9. Jorgensen, M and Philips. *Discourse Analysis as Theory and Method*. London, 2002.